

Wrocław, the capital of *Astrapaesus ulmi* (Rossi) (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae)

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ABSTRACT. Wrocław, the capital of *Astrapaesus ulmi* (Rossi) (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae).

Seventeen specimens of the rare rove beetle *Astrapaesus ulmi* (Rossi) are recorded from Wrocław, collected or observed in recent years. Most of them were found in urban environment, including the city center, mainly on walkways. A recent colonization of this primarily Mediterranean species seems well-supported by the lack of any specimens from this area preserved at the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław. We discuss the urban island heat effect as the presumable phenomenon facilitating the occurrence of thermophiles in Wrocław and surrounding areas.

KEY WORDS: Staphylinoidea, Staphylinini, Cyртоquediina, new records, Poland, Isopoda.

INTRODUCTION

Astrapaesus ulmi (Rossi, 1790) is the sole Polish member of the rove beetle subtribe Cyртоquediina of Staphylinini. The species is distributed primarily in the northern part of the Mediterranean Basin, with a few records from northern countries (e.g., Belgium, Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Slovakia, Czech Rep., Poland), and it occurs also in the Asian region of Turkey (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015, see also PIETRYKOWSKA-TUDRUJ *et al.* 2014). In Poland, it is regarded as an extremely rare beetle. The first record was published nearly 130 years ago based on a finding in Kraków (RYBIŃSKI 1897), but HORION (1965) listed this locality with a question mark. The next author who found many specimens in the same city was WOJAS (2011). Subsequently, JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2018) found a single specimen in Wrocław, and WOJAS *et al.* (2019) recorded this species from Opole, Kraków-Kleparz, Kraków-Olsza and Stasiówka in the Western Beskid Mts.

During the past few years, *Astrapaesus ulmi* was collected or observed many times in Wrocław, making it the Polish capital of this rare species. New records are given below:

– **Lower Silesia:** XS36, Wrocław Maślice, allotment of ROD Tęcza, 6 VI 2023, 1 ex., on the ground, leg. & coll. M. Wanat; Wrocław, crossing of Legnicka-Zachodnia Sts., 4 V 2024, 1 ex. on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, crossing Strzegomska-Stacyjna Sts., 6 VII 2023, 1 ex., 21 VI 2024, 1 ex., all on walkways, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, Stacyjna St., 22 V 2024, 1 ex., 27 V 2024, 1 ex., 11 VII 2024, 1 ex., all on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, Robotnicza St., 10 VII 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, Strzegomska St., 12

VIII 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, Nadrzeczna St. 35 m S of Las Pilczycki Forest, 27 VIII 2024, 1 ex., on the ground, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, Las Pilczycki Forest, forest section 3, 2 VI 2023, 2 exx., under bark of a dead *Ulmus minor* MILL., leg. & coll. R. Ruta; XS37, Wrocław Świniary, bus end stop, 27 VI 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; XS46, Wrocław Center, Bema Sq., 3 X 2020, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. M. Wanat; Wrocław, Boya-Żeleńskiego St., bus stop, 18 V 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, obs. P. Jałoszyński; Wrocław, near Voivodship Office, 16 VIII 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński; XS47, Wrocław Polanowice, Bierzycka St., 26 VI 2024, 1 ex., on walkway, leg. & coll. R. Ruta.

Fig. 1. Collecting sites of *Astrapaeus ulmi* in Wrocław (map generated with QGIS 3.34.7-Prizren software, basemap source: <http://mapy.geoportal.gov.pl/>).

Ryc. 1. Miejsca poławiania *Astrapaeus ulmi* we Wrocławiu (mapa przygotowana w programie QGIS 3.34.7-Prizren, źródło podkładu: <http://mapy.geoportal.gov.pl/>).

DISCUSSION

Seventeen specimens collected or observed in Wrocław by three coleopterists, mainly during their regular walking activities and not as a result of focused collecting efforts, suggest that *A. ulmi* is a relatively common species in this large city (Fig. 1). ROSSI (1790), who described this species based on material from Italy, stated that “*saepius inveni sub cortice Ulmi primo vere*”, that is, “I have seen it in the spring under the bark of the elm trees.” Only two specimens collected in Wrocław were found under a bark of the elm (*Ulmus minor* MILL.) in the Las Pilczycki Forest. All remaining findings are either in a strictly urban environment (mainly on walkways) or in/near allotments. Lawns and other areas covered with vegetation are along or close to the urban localities where *A. ulmi* was particularly frequently encountered, and the streets Legnicka, Stacyjna, Robotnicza and Strzegomska are close to the railway line. Larvae of *A. ulmi* were reported to feed on immature Isopoda (PIETRYKOWSKA-TUDRUJ *et al.* 2014), and many isopods were observed by the first author on walkways where adults of this beetle were found. In most localities *Armadillidium vulgare* LATREILLE, *Porcellio scaber* LATREILLE, and *P. spinicornis* SAY were found, and on the Stacyjna St. also *Armadillidium nasatum* BUDDE-LUND, inhabiting mainly the railway embankment along the street. Specimens listed by WOJAS *et al.* (2019) from Kraków-Kleparz, and Kraków-Olsza were also found on walkways in an urban environment, and a similar record was published by KREISSL (1987).

Astrapaeus ulmi (Figs 2, 3) seems to occur in a variety of remarkably different environments. Besides two large Polish cities, Kraków and Wrocław, in northern countries it was collected in hollow trees and under bark (REDTENBACHER 1874, GANGLBAUER 1895), under decaying plant matter in moist sites (REITTER 1909), on riverside areas (FÜLÖP 2005, STAN 2005), under cliffs on a coastline (HANCE 2007), in a limestone quarry (WOJAS 2011), in an open agricultural land (SCHÜLKE & FLÜGEL 2015), in a calcareous grassland (HOFFMANN & BOETZL 2018), and on banks of a pond that fills a former cement factory excavation (WOJAS *et al.* 2019).

Astrapaeus ulmi was treated in Germany as an extinct species (GEISER 1998) until SCHÜLKE & FLÜGEL (2015) recorded ten specimens collected in pitfall traps in Hessen. Based on this and other new records from other countries, SCHÜLKE & FLÜGEL (2015) conclude that *A. ulmi* recently expanded its distribution into northern areas. The data from Wrocław corroborate this view. The Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (MNHW) holds large beetle collections of the pre-war Silesian entomologists, who intensively collected in Lower Silesia, including the city of Wrocław (JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* 2014). However, not a single specimen of *A. ulmi* from this region is present in the MNHW historical collections. *Astrapaeus ulmi* is an easily identifiable species, and slightly similar species of *Quedius* STEPHENS are numerous in MNHW and have been correctly identified by their owners. The only reason why *A. ulmi* was not found and recorded from Lower Silesia before 1945 is that it was not present there.

The warming tendency in Wrocław was studied by BRYŚ & BRYŚ (2010), who found out that a strong increasing tendency began after 1956, and in the years 1956-2007 it amounted

Figs. 2, 3. *Astrapaeus ulmi* photographed in Wrocław Polanowice (photo R. Ruta).

Ryc. 2, 3. *Astrapaeus ulmi* sfotografowany we Wrocławiu Polanowicach (fot. R. Ruta).

to 3.2°C/100 years. They also demonstrated that changes in the winter time were of a decisive importance. They concluded that the urban heat island effect began to exert a major impact in the 1980s. This is very likely one of factors facilitating warm-loving species to colonize and maintain populations in Wrocław. Some recent discoveries of rare or never previously collected thermophiles (e.g., WANAT 2002, WANAT *et al.* 2022, JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2024, LEWEK & KADEJ 2024) support this hypothesis.

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Streszczenie

Wrocław, stolica *Astrapaeus ulmi* (Rossi) (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae)

Astrapaeus ulmi (Rossi) jest gatunkiem głównie śródziemnomorskim, z niewielką liczbą stanowisk znanych z państw Europy północnej (poza Skandynawią) i środkowej. W Polsce został po raz pierwszy wykazany blisko 130 lat temu z Krakowa, a później dopiero w 2011, z tego samego miasta. Wrocław był drugim znanym z Polski miejscem występowania tego kusaka, opublikowanym w 2018. Krótco później kolejne znaleziska odnotowano z Krakowa oraz Stasiówki w Beskidzie Zachodnim. Kilkanaście stanowisk, na których znaleziono *A. ulmi* w ciągu ostatnich kilku lat na terenie Wrocławia jest przedmiotem niniejszej pracy. Tak liczne występowanie w warunkach miejskich (większość to osobniki poławiane na chodnikach, również w centrum miasta) jest niezwykle i sugeruje, że efekt wyspy ciepła, udokumentowany w innych publikacjach, sprzyja kolonizacji przez gatunki ciepłolubne. Brak okazów *A. ulmi* z Dolnego Śląska (i ogólnie z Polski) w historycznych zbiorach Muzeum Przyrodniczego UWrocław potwierdza nową falę współczesnej kolonizacji.

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